

1 Photovoltaic generation on vertical façades in urban context from open 2 satellite-derived solar resource data

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12 **Abstract**

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15 Solar radiation incident at building façades and elements in an urban context is essential in
16 determining the energy production on building rooftops and vertical façades. The proper
17 determination of solar irradiance incident on a vertical façade needs quality input of the
18 components of solar radiation and a high resolution digital surface model with the heights of
19 buildings and other elements in the urban area of study. In this work a thorough methodology
20 for modeling PV generation, in hourly basis, at building façades with open available data and
21 methods is presented. Hourly data of satellite-derived solar irradiance is used with high
22 resolution digital model from LIDAR information to estimate with the Sandia model the PV
23 generation of five small arrays at west, south and east façades of a building in Madrid. PV
24 output modeled for west and south arrays are in rather good agreement with the monitored
25 experimental data of the production. RMSE of 8% and 12% was observed for the monthly
26 power predicted for west and south facades, respectively. The east façade case was much
27 more challenging due to variability of shadows it receives from the nearby large deciduous
28 trees throughout the year, which results in high uncertainty in the shading influence
29 estimation. Anyway, the methodology proves the benefits and possibilities of detailed
30 estimation of PV production in building façades from open available information regarding
31 both solar resource, open modeling tools and urban topography, even in a very challenging
32 conditions associated to the variability of trees canopy.
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35 **Keywords:** BIPV; PV modeling; Solar Radiation databases; Sky View Factor; Digital Surface
36 Model; partial shading of PV arrays
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38 **1. Introduction**

39
40 Solar photovoltaics (PV) and solar thermal systems deployments in urban environments are
41 gaining interest as drivers of decentralization of electricity and heat production. Both are key
42 elements in the concept of Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (nZEB) aimed at achieving buildings
43 almost independent from the external electrical grid through proper designed features and the
44 use of renewable energy sources (Marszal et al., 2011). In the case of PV, the International
45 Energy Agency, through the Task 15 of the programme IEA-PVPS (PVPS, 2021), is gathering

46 efforts in promoting and accelerating the penetration of both BIPV (Building Integrated
47 PhotoVoltaics) and BAPV (Building Applied PhotoVoltaics), and delivering updated reports on
48 important aspects as regulation, definition and characterization, user needs and research.
49 Solar potential studies in urban landscape can include ground, roofs and vertical façades of
50 buildings.

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52 Many studies in the literature dealt with solar potential estimation on rooftops using
53 geographic information systems (GIS) to incorporate the influence of urban obstructions to the
54 incoming solar radiation (Bódis et al., 2019; Brito et al., 2012; Jakubiec and Reinhart, 2013;
55 Khan and Arsalan, 2016; Singh and Banerjee, 2015; Verso et al., 2015). However, in the past
56 recent years additional studies include methodologies for estimating solar potential also in
57 vertical façades (Catita et al., 2014; Desthieux et al., 2018; Hofierka and Zlocha, 2012; Lindberg
58 et al., 2015; Lou et al., 2016; Redweik et al., 2013). A thorough review on modeling the solar
59 potential in urban context can be found in the recent literature (Freitas et al., 2015). Recent
60 studies combine GIS, physics models and machine learning algorithms at national scale
61 (Assouline et al., 2018; Walch et al., 2020). Moreover, recent contributions are conducting also
62 to the availability of open and powerful tools broadening the possibilities of new studies and
63 analysis. For instance this is the case of SEBE (Solar Energy on Building Envelopes) model which
64 is incorporated in UMEP (Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor), a plugin for QGIS
65 software (QGIS, 2021). SEBE model estimates solar irradiance on ground surfaces, building
66 roofs and walls from digital surface model (DSM) and solar position (Lindberg et al., 2015; Ratti
67 and Richens, 1999).

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69 The models and tools for estimating solar potential in complex urban environment require also
70 detailed information of solar resource. Solar radiation data on vertical surfaces are not
71 generally available from measurements and the procedure involves having data of the three
72 components of solar irradiance for horizontal surface: Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI),
73 Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) and Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DIF). Then, the subsequent
74 use of transposition models is needed afterwards to derive the incident solar irradiance at
75 vertical surfaces. The accuracy and quality of the initial solar radiation data plays a significant
76 role on the final uncertainty since there are many intermediate steps in the procedure of
77 estimating solar irradiance incident on façades. Satellite-derived solar irradiance data is
78 probably the best choice nowadays since there are several high quality products that are freely
79 available (Polo and Perez, 2019; Sengupta et al., 2017). Time series of GHI, DNI and DIF can be
80 obtained on an hourly basis from several databases with rather good quality (de Freitas
81 Moscardini Júnior and Rüther, 2020; Huld et al., 2012; Polo et al., 2020; Psiloglou et al., 2020;
82 Riihelä et al., 2015; Urraca et al., 2017; Yang, 2018; Yang and Bright, 2020). Afterwards,
83 transposition models are then needed to estimating solar irradiance at an inclined and
84 arbitrarily oriented surface using the three components (GHI, DNI, DIF) as input. There is a very
85 large list of transposition models elsewhere and recent studies contain useful information on
86 their accuracy and associated difficulties and problems (Gueymard and Ruiz-Arias, 2016; Yang,
87 2016).

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89 This work presents a thorough methodology for modeling in detail the PV generation of five
90 small PV arrays placed at the vertical façades of a building in Madrid using as input open
91 satellite-derived solar radiation data and LIDAR information. A DSM is built from the LIDAR
92 data to estimate shading and the corresponding sky view factor (SVF). Two years of hourly
93 solar radiation is used as input to derive solar irradiance in high detail for the façades of the
94 building. Most works in the literature employ GIS for studying the potential mainly on rooftops
95 and less frequently in facades in terms of yearly values or annual yield, but very few studies
96 presents estimations at hourly basis and assessment with real monitored PV arrays working on
97 facades of a building. The results show the benefit of the methodology for modeling the PV

98 generation of modules at façades and also evidence the potential problems associated to the
99 presence of large trees near the façade that may affect to the proper shading effect
100 determination; particularly interesting is the case of deciduous trees, which opacity changes
101 throughout the year.
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103 2. Description of the case study and experimental data

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105 The building under study is the so-called *Building 42* of Ciemat headquarters area,
106 placed in the university campus in Madrid (40.4551° North, -3.73° East). This building
107 houses five individual small PV arrays (each one connected to a different single
108 inverter) distributed in the upper part of the east, south and west façades. The
109 orientation of the building is slightly deviated to the west (about 9°) and thus the
110 façades azimuth are 351°, 81°, 171° and 262° for façades north, east, south and west,
111 respectively. Figure 1 shows the domain area used in this work and pictures of the PV
112 arrays in façades east, south and west. The east façade contains three identical PV
113 arrays of 7x2p modules (named East_S, East_C and East_N arrays, respectively), the
114 south façade has one array of 7x4p modules, and the west façade includes one 8x2p
115 PV array. Table 1 summarizes the module and inverter characteristics of all the arrays.
116 Additional details on the building structures, PV systems and monitoring can be found
117 in a previous descriptive work (Martín-Chivelet et al., 2018).

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123 Figure 1. a) Area of study of Ciemat headquarters. b) East façade with three PV arrays
124 highlighted. c) South façade with the corresponding PV array. d) West façade with the
125 PV array used in this work.

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Table 1. Main characteristics of the PV arrays

Array	Configuration	Module	Power (W)	Inverter	Power (kW)
East_N	7sx2p	SunPower E20-327	327	Fronius IG Plus 50 V-1	4
East_C	7sx2p	SunPower E20-327	327	Fronius IG Plus 50 V-1	4
East_S	7sx2p	SunPower E20-327	327	Fronius IG Plus 50 V-1	4
South	7sx4p	SunPower E18-325	305	Fronius IG Plus 100 V-3	8
West	8sx2p	SunPower E20-327	327	Fronius IG Plus 50 V-1	4

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Different electrical parameters of each array as well as some local meteorological variables are being monitored. In particular, voltage, current and power of each inverter are available. In addition, module temperature of one single module from each array is measured using T type thermocouples. Global horizontal irradiance (GHI) is measured in the rooftop of the building with a thermopile pyranometer and vertical irradiance in east, south and west orientations of the building are also recorded by several calibrated cells placed at the top of a mast in the building rooftop (Figure 2). Unfortunately there were not available long and quality measurements of direct normal irradiance (DNI) and diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI). Figure 2 shows also how the modules were integrated and fastened to the façade in the upgrading work of the building. PV modules are integrated into the upper areas of a new ventilated façade, built as part of the rehabilitation project for Ciemat building 42, which was aimed at improving the building's structural condition and energy efficiency. PV modules occupy a total surface area of about 176 m².

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Figure 2. a) Mast placed at the building rooftop with calibrated cells for measuring vertical irradiance at east, south and west orientations. b) Solar panels integration with the façade.

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3. Solar resource data

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The basic solar resource data used as input in this work consisted of two years (2017 and 2018) of hourly data of the three solar irradiance components (GHI, DNI and DIF) delivered by CAMS (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service) Radiation Service with a spatial resolution of 3 km at nadir (Schroedter-Homscheidt et al., 2019). CAMS Radiation Service (Copernicus, 2021) is a high quality database of solar irradiance

160 based on Heliosat-4 methodology (Qu et al., 2017). The method combined the cloud
161 properties derived from Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) satellites with fast
162 radiative transfer model McClear (Lefèvre et al., 2013). CAMS GHI hourly data
163 compared with the GHI measurements on the building rooftop resulted in mean bias
164 deviation (MBD) of -0.5 % and root mean square deviation (RMSD) of 17.4 %. Figure 3
165 shows a scatter plot for the assessment of GHI delivered by CAMS Radiation Service for
166 the period 2017-2018; the corresponding R^2 for this scatter plot is 0.95. Despite there
167 is no quality measurements of DNI for evaluating the uncertainty of DNI derived by
168 CAMS Radiation Service it is expected to be higher than the uncertainty for GHI. For
169 instance, evaluation of CAMS radiation service in several ground stations in Morocco
170 resulted in RMSD for hourly DNI in the range of 26-39% (Marchand et al., 2018).
171 Nevertheless, it should be remarked that CAMS Radiation Service is one of the best
172 and more accurate free and open products for solar radiation data derived from
173 satellite imagery (Yang and Bright, 2020).
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177 Figure 3. Scatter plot of hourly GHI estimated by CAMS vs. experimental
178 measurements in Building 42.

179 4. Solar irradiance at vertical façades

180 4.1 Sky view factor and Shadow calculation

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183 The sky view factor (SVF) is a simple parameter describing the part of the sky that is
184 not obscured by the surroundings for a given point (Lindberg and Grimmond, 2010). It
185 can be defined as the ratio of the sky hemisphere visible from the ground (Bernard,
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188 2018). The SVF and the shadowing in the façades of a building can be computed from a
 189 high-resolution digital surface model (DSM) derived from LIDAR data. LIDAR data offers
 190 the height of a ground area with very high resolution (including buildings, trees,
 191 structures, etc). In Spain LIDAR data is supplied by the Spanish Geographic Institute
 192 (IGN) through a download service (Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica, 2021).

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194 In this work a DSM of the area under study is obtained with the use of LASTools (a
 195 powerful library for reading and extracting information from compressed LIDAR files)
 196 and QGIS. The resulting raster DSM of the area of Ciemat including the *Building 42* and
 197 surrounding buildings, elements and trees is shown in figure 4. The DSM shown in this
 198 figure covers the same area of that shown in Figure 1 a), so that the identification of
 199 the building under study in figures 4 a) and b) is straightforward. It should be remarked
 200 that north and east façades of the building have many large trees placed close to the
 201 building, while south and west-south façades have mainly other buildings in the
 202 surroundings.

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205 Figure 4. a) Geotiff raster of DSM. b) 3-D view of DSM.

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207 Four artificial façades for the target building have been created by selecting the
 208 corresponding x-utm and y-utm coordinates of the points delimiting each building
 209 façade in the DSM with a resolution of around 25 cm in length and 0.5 m in height. The
 210 total height of each artificial façade is 15 m, so that it is higher than the actual façades
 211 heights of 8 and 10 m, depending on the façade. Thus a façade is a matrix of 31 rows
 212 (denoting points at different heights) by 150-175 columns (defined by x-utm and y-utm
 213 coordinates of the real façades).

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215 For each point (i, j) in the façade matrix, the SVF for the façade F is computed by the
 216 following expression (Böhner and Antonić, 2009):

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$$218 \quad SVF^F(i, j) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [\cos\beta \cos^2\phi_n(i, j) + \sin\beta \cos(n - \alpha_F)(90 - \phi_n(i, j) - \sin\phi_n(i, j)\cos\phi_n(i, j))]. \quad (1)$$

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Where N is 360° , β is the tilt angle of the surface (90° for a vertical façade), n is a direction in azimuth (it ranges from 1 to 360 in steps of 1°), α_F is the azimuth of the façade F , and $\phi_n(i, j)$ is the horizon angle of point (i, j) in the azimuth direction determined by n . The horizon angle $\phi_n(i, j)$ is determined by the angle of elevation of the highest obstacle (point in the DSM) that the point (i, j) views in the azimuth determined by n .

Figure 5 shows the SVF computed for the four façades of *Building 42* taking into account the obstacles in the area delimited by the DSM. It can be clearly appreciated the strong influence of the large trees on the North-East corner of the building.

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Figure 5. SVF computed for the four façades of CIEMAT Building 42.

Shadows are computed in hourly basis for each element of the façade (25 cm wide and 50 cm in height) as a parameter, that can only takes two values, $Sh=1$ if the element is illuminated and $Sh=0$ if the element is shadowed. Thus, for every façade we have a matrix of shadow for every hour indicating which elements in the façade are completely shadowed and which ones are completely illuminated every hour.

4.2 Solar irradiance at vertical façades

In order to estimate the incident hourly solar irradiance at each point of the façade F we have assumed the following approach,

$$G^F(i, j) = DNI \cos(AOI) Sh(i, j) + Diff^F(i, j) + \frac{1}{2} \rho^F GHI , \quad (2)$$

where AOI is the angle of incidence which depends on the solar elevation and azimuth angles and on the surface's tilt (90° for every façade) and azimuth angles, $Diff^F(i, j)$ is the sky diffuse irradiance for the element (i, j) of façade F , and ρ^F is the effective albedo for façade F , defined here as the average albedo of the ground and surrounding surfaces that can reflect solar irradiance towards the façade (the values of 0.2 has been chosen for the effective albedo). Therefore, the incident solar irradiance on the façade element is the sum of three contributions, the direct irradiance projected to the surface taking into account the shading, the sky diffuse irradiance and the reflected irradiance due to ground and other surfaces and elements in the surrounding. The Diffuse irradiance is computed from the three components of horizontal irradiance by the Perez model with modifications to take into account the sky view factor of each element in the façade (Perez et al., 1990, 1987). The sky diffuse irradiance is then estimated by,

$$Diff^F(i, j) = Cir^F Sh(i, j) + DIF SVF^F(i, j) + Hor^F , \quad (3)$$

being Cir^F and Hor^F are the circumsolar diffuse component and horizon brightening diffuse component of the solar radiation estimated by Perez model, respectively. Therefore, the main modification to the original Perez model for tilt surface consisted on taking into account the shading in the circumsolar diffuse component and the sky view factor of every façade element in the isotropic diffuse irradiance instead of the sky view factor determined only by the tilt angle (0.5 for the case of a vertical surface). Therefore, using the GHI, DNI and DIF satellite-derived components provided by CAMS Radiation Service as input and the sky view factor and shading estimated from the DSM is suitable to estimate the incident solar irradiance at each façade element.

4.3 Evaluation of solar radiation estimations at façades

In order to evaluate the uncertainty of the solar irradiance estimations made on the building façades we have compared them with the measurements of the calibrated solar cells placed at the top of a mast on the building rooftop (Figure 2). The corresponding MBE, RMSD and MAD (Mean Absolute Deviation) are shown in table 2. Figure 6 shows the east, south and west solar irradiance estimated compared with measurements in hourly basis for a few days and the corresponding scatter plots. The R^2 estimated for these scatter plots were 0.73, 0.89 and 0.90 for the east, south and west facades, respectively.

295 Table 2. Error metrics for solar irradiance estimated at vertical façades

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Façade	MBD (%)	RMSD (%)	MAD (%)
East	5.7	57.3	32.0
South	5.6	29.8	18.4
West	-6.2	32.1	18.8

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298 As shown in both the table and the scatter plots of figure 6 much higher uncertainty
299 resulted in the estimations of solar irradiance at the east façade. As a consequence
300 much higher uncertainties are also expected in modeling those PV arrays placed on
301 east façade.

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303 The scatter plot for east façade shows a set of data that are particularly
304 underestimated (Figure 6). This underestimation is due to the uncertainty associated
305 to the large deciduous trees in front of the east façade of the building. On the one
306 hand, DSM information that comes from LIDAR data might not include recent possible
307 changes in the natural vegetal cover (i.e. tree pruning), or refurbishment works after
308 LIDAR flights; on the other, during fall and winter seasons the deciduous trees opacity
309 is much less than in spring and summer, and consequently direct radiation can reach
310 the wall of the building while the modeling calculates a shadowing. Therefore, the line
311 of deciduous trees close to the east facade, taller than the building height, is very
312 challenging for modeling both the solar irradiance and the PV generation at the façade.

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318 Figure 6. Solar irradiance estimated for the vertical façades compared with

319 experimental data. a) Example of several days. b) scatter plot of hourly data.

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321 5. Modeling the PV generation at the three façades

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323 The energy generation of the five PV arrays listed in table 1 has been modeled for two

324 years (2017 and 2018) with the Sandia Array Performance Model (SAPM) using as

325 input the solar irradiance, in hourly basis, estimated at the façade points, with a

326 resolution of 50x25 cm, and the module temperature measured at each array. Back
327 panel temperature was measured with one thermocouple for every array at the rear
328 side of the modules, and was directly input to the SAPM model. SAPM is available
329 under the PV Performance Modeling Collaborative initiative (King et al., 2007, 2004).
330 SAPM model is included in the PV lib library that can be freely downloaded from the
331 PVPCM site (PVPCM, 2021) and has shown to be very flexible and accurate (Gurupira
332 and Rix, 2017; Polo et al., 2016; Stein and Farnung, 2017).

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334 Since the irradiance incident at each array varies along the surface due to shading, the
335 DC part of the PV generation has been modeled individually for every single module in
336 the array and then the array configuration has been taken into account for estimating
337 the DC generation of the whole array. Thus, SAPM model is used to model the DC
338 power of every single module in the array using as input the average incoming solar
339 irradiance over the module area and the module temperature measured (we have only
340 one measuring point for the module temperature for each array). Modeling partial
341 shading in PV arrays is complex and can involve to deal module by module, or cell by
342 cell, with the whole I-V curve (Alonso-García et al., 2006; Alqaisi and Mahmoud, 2019;
343 Galeano et al., 2018; Seyedmahmoudian et al., 2013). Shading losses depend on the
344 series-parallel configuration of the array, the number and distribution of by-pass and
345 blocking diodes and on the shading profile (Alonso-García et al., 1997). Due to the
346 complexity of the problem and the uncertainties in determining accurately the shading
347 and the limitations of the SAPM model it was required the adoption of approximations
348 to explore the capabilities of simple and fast models in modeling these arrays at the
349 different façades.

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351 Two different approaches have been explored to model the array power generation
352 under complex and irregular shading effects. The first one, denoted as Model 1,
353 assumes that each string in the array is working with the maximum current as it would
354 not be affected by shading, and the AC power is finally multiplied by the fraction of the
355 area that is shaded to account for the reduction of power due to shading. The
356 approach of assuming that the power reduction is equal to the shaded array fraction is
357 the most optimistic and represent the minimum limit for power reduction (Martínez-
358 Moreno et al., 2010; Masa-Bote and Caamaño-Martín, 2014). The second approach,
359 denoted as Model 2, assumes that the string working current is limited by the shaded
360 modules and then the minimum current of module is assumed for the whole string,
361 and consequently the AC power of the array is not multiplied by any shading factor at
362 all.

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364 Figure 7 shows the daily generation of each array during for the two years modeled.
365 Arrays at west and south façades are generally better modeled than those at east
366 façade. The power output in west and south arrays was predicted with a RMSE of 15%
367 and 21%, respectively, in daily basis, and in monthly basis the RMSE was 8% and 12%,
368 respectively. In addition, it can be observed that the uncertainty in estimating the daily
369 production varies along the length of the east façade. The highest differences between
370 experimental and modeled energy production are found in the north part of the east
371 façade (the so called East_N array). Figure 8 shows the box plot of the differences

372 between hourly experimental power and hourly modeled power with model 2 for each
373 array.
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378 Figure 7. Daily energy production of PV arrays at façades compared to the monitored
379 data.
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384 Figure 8. Box plot of differences between experimental and modeled power in hourly
385 basis.

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387 In the case of the three arrays placed at the east façade the modeling results with the
388 Model 1 show a general overestimation of the energy throughout the whole year,

389 excepting the case of array East_N (placed at the north part of the façade), where the
390 trend is a general and significant underestimation. However, the results of the Model 2
391 show higher agreement with the experimental data in arrays East_S and East_Mid, but
392 larger underestimations of the output power in array East_N during spring and
393 summer. The Model 2 approach has more physical meaning since the shaded modules
394 limit the final current in the string they form part of, and thus a better performance
395 was expected. However, the large uncertainties in these arrays at the east façade
396 evidence the uncertainties in the shading determination due to irregular and changing
397 shading conditions produced by the surrounding trees.

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399 Therefore, this apparently opposite behavior in the predictions of arrays placed at the
400 same façade can be only explained by the different shading modeled along the year, its
401 dynamics and variability, and the impact on the challenging conditions imposed to the
402 array. Thus, the irregular and dynamic conditions of the shading caused by the
403 deciduous trees in front of the east façade make it quite difficult to model accurately
404 the arrays generation by using simple performance models as SAPM. In addition to the
405 propagation of the initial uncertainty of solar radiation components derived from a
406 satellite model, one even most important contributor to the uncertainty is the impact
407 of the limitations in the DSM obtained from LIDAR information. Thus, the information
408 in the digital model corresponds to a steady picture of the heights of surrounding
409 objects. Figure 9 shows a picture of the whole east façade in a summer morning where
410 irregular characteristics of the shading can be clearly observed. As can be seen in the
411 picture in front of the east-north façade there is a dry tree without leaves that would
412 explain the underestimation of the energy generated by the array East_N. Thus,
413 according to the DSM there is a large tree there, which implies a tall obstacle to the
414 incoming solar irradiance while the actual situation is different. That tree is actually
415 rather transparent to the incoming solar irradiance and the underestimation observed
416 in the calculation is due to erroneous computation of the shading in that part of the
417 building. In addition, in the DSM it can be observed two additional trees at the north-
418 east corner of the building that no longer exist (see and compare figure 4 and the
419 picture in figure 9). Indeed, the trees shown in the east-north corner of the building
420 were removed before the installation of the PV modules in the building façades,
421 indicating that the LIDAR information available for the area of study is not updated to
422 the show the refurbishment works performed in the building in 2016. In addition,
423 figure 10 illustrates the shadow induced by the trees, modeled from the DSM data, for
424 three different hours in a single day, where it can be appreciated the irregular shapes
425 of the shadows.

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Figure 9. Irregular shading on the east facade caused by trees in a summer morning.

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Figure 10. Computed shadows on east façade for three different hours (12:00, 15:00 and 18:00) on a 15th may 2018.

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5. Conclusions

Detailed modeling of PV generation at the façades of a building in urban environment requires of both time series of solar irradiance components with good quality and high resolution information on the morphology of the environment to allow shadow casting estimates. There are several open databases of solar radiation data derived from satellite imagery that can be effectively used for that purpose. In addition, the urban morphology can be obtained from LIDAR data to create DSM at high resolution with the heights of buildings, canopies, trees and other structures. This work presents a methodology for modeling PV generation on building façades based entirely on open and free data and methods available. Solar resource basic input consisted of time series of the solar radiation components, in hourly basis, supplied by CAMS Radiation Service for two years (2017 and 2018). Open GIS tools and LIDAR data have been used to create a DSM of a selected area in the university campus of Madrid. Shading and sky view factor have been then computed, from the DSM, for the façades of a selected building in the area of study, where five small PV arrays are installed in façades west, south and east, and monitored. Thus, detailed estimations of incident solar irradiance at each point of every façade are performed by combining shading and SVF parameters with Perez transposition model. Finally, modeling of PV generation of each array was performed by using the SAPM model implemented in PV lib open tool. The methodology presented here thus is aimed at proving that by using free public data and models it is possible to perform a thorough analysis of the PV generation at a building façade in Madrid City. Notwithstanding the study did not need a priori of satellite derived irradiance, since we has measurements of incident irradiance at three directions, the use of open satellite data allows to remark the potentiality of the methodology for future extension at large scale.

The results of PV modeling at façades shown in this work have proven the benefit of this methodology for façades in buildings. The west and south arrays were modeled with good results. However, challenging boundary conditions regarding large deciduous trees close to the east façade have evidenced large uncertainties and difficulties in proper modeling the PV arrays due to the changes throughout the year of trees opacity. On the other hand, recent changes of removing some trees are not contemplated in the DSM since LIDAR data provides information before 2016 (year of refurbishment of the building and surroundings). In other words the static feature of the DSM limits somehow its use in modeling those facades that might be affected by dynamic changes in the surrounding tress and vegetation. The impact of this dynamic partial shading on the arrays at east façade requires a more detailed analysis and the use of complex models that account better for partial shading effects. Future work motivated from these results will be focused on better modeling the performance of these arrays at east façade under the challenging conditions imposed by the presence of large trees in the surroundings.

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491 (Solar Resource), where the authors collaborate.

492

493 **References**

494

- 495 Alonso-García, M.C., Arribas, L.M., Chenlo, F., Cruz, I., 1997. Shading Effect on a Roof
496 Integrated Grid-Connected PV Plant, in: 14th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy
497 Conference, EUPVSEC. Barcelona, Spain.
- 498 Alonso-García, M.C., Ruiz, J.M., Herrmann, W., 2006. Computer simulation of shading effects in
499 photovoltaic arrays. *Renewable Energy* 31, 1986–1993.
500 doi:10.1016/j.renene.2005.09.030
- 501 Alqaisi, Z., Mahmoud, Y., 2019. Comprehensive Study of Partially Shaded PV Modules with
502 Overlapping Diodes. *IEEE Access* 7, 172665–172675. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2956916
- 503 Assouline, D., Mohajeri, N., Scartezzini, J.L., 2018. Large-scale rooftop solar photovoltaic
504 technical potential estimation using Random Forests. *Applied Energy* 217, 189–211.
505 doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.02.118
- 506 Bernard, J., 2018. Sky View Factor Calculation in Urban Context : Computational Performance
507 and Accuracy Analysis of Two Open and Free GIS Tools. *climate* 6. doi:10.3390/cli6030060
- 508 Bódis, K., Kougias, I., Jäger-Waldau, A., Taylor, N., Szabó, S., 2019. A high-resolution geospatial
509 assessment of the rooftop solar photovoltaic potential in the European Union.
510 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 114, 109309. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2019.109309
- 511 Böhner, J., Antonić, O., 2009. Land-surface parameters specific to topo-climatology.
512 *Developments in Soil Science* 33, 195–226. doi:10.1016/S0166-2481(08)00008-1
- 513 Brito, M.C., Gomes, N., Santos, T., Tenedório, J.A., 2012. Photovoltaic potential in a Lisbon
514 suburb using LiDAR data. *Solar Energy* 86, 283–288. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2011.09.031
- 515 Catita, C., Redweik, P., Pereira, J., Brito, M.C., 2014. Extending solar potential analysis in
516 buildings to vertical facades. *Computers & Geosciences* 66, 1–12.
517 doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2014.01.002
- 518 Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica, 2021. Centro de Descargas [WWW Document].
519 URL <http://centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/> (accessed 6.8.21).
- 520 Copernicus, 2021. CAMS Radiation Service [WWW Document]. URL [http://www.soda-](http://www.soda-pro.com/es/web-services/radiation/cams-radiation-service)
521 [pro.com/es/web-services/radiation/cams-radiation-service](http://www.soda-pro.com/es/web-services/radiation/cams-radiation-service) (accessed 6.8.21).
- 522 de Freitas Moscardini Júnior, E., Rütther, R., 2020. The influence of the solar radiation database
523 and the photovoltaic simulator on the sizing and economics of photovoltaic-diesel
524 generators. *Energy Conversion and Management* 210, 112737.
525 doi:10.1016/j.enconman.2020.112737
- 526 Desthieux, G., Carneiro, C., Camponovo, R., Ineichen, P., Morello, E., Boulmier, A.,
527 Abdennadher, N., Dervev, S., Ellert, C., 2018. Solar energy potential assessment on
528 rooftops and facades in large built environments based on lidar data, image processing,
529 and cloud computing. Methodological background, application, and validation in geneva
530 (solar cadaster). *Frontiers in Built Environment* 4. doi:10.3389/fbuil.2018.00014
- 531 Freitas, S., Catita, C., Redweik, P., Brito, M.C.C., 2015. Modelling solar potential in the urban
532 environment: State-of-the-art review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 41,
533 915–931. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.08.060
- 534 Galeano, A.G., Bressan, M., Vargas, F.J., Alonso, C., 2018. Shading ratio impact on photovoltaic

535 modules and correlation with shading patterns. *Energies* 11, 1–26.
536 doi:10.3390/en11040852

537 Gueymard, C.A., Ruiz-Arias, J.A., 2016. Extensive worldwide validation and climate sensitivity
538 analysis of direct irradiance predictions from 1-min global irradiance. *Solar Energy*.
539 doi:10.1016/j.solener.2015.10.010

540 Gurupira, T., Rix, A.J., 2017. PV Simulation Software Comparisons : Pvsyst , Nrel Sam and Pvlib,
541 in: SAUPEC 2017.

542 Hofierka, J., Zlocha, M., 2012. A New 3-D Solar Radiation Model for 3-D City Models.
543 *Transactions in GIS* 16, 681–690. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9671.2012.01337.x

544 Huld, T., Müller, R., Gambardella, A., 2012. A new solar radiation database for estimating PV
545 performance in Europe and Africa. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2012.03.006

546 Jakubiec, J.A., Reinhart, C.F., 2013. A method for predicting city-wide electricity gains from
547 photovoltaic panels based on LiDAR and GIS data combined with hourly Daysim
548 simulations. *Solar Energy* 93, 127–143. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2013.03.022

549 Khan, J., Arsalan, M.H., 2016. Estimation of rooftop solar photovoltaic potential using geo-
550 spatial techniques: A perspective from planned neighborhood of Karachi - Pakistan.
551 *Renewable Energy* 90, 188–203. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2015.12.058

552 King, D.L., Boyson, W.E., Kratochvill, J.A., 2004. Photovoltaic Array Performance Model. Sandia
553 Report. doi:10.2172/919131

554 King, D.L., Gonzalez, S., Galbraith, G.M., Boyson, W.E., 2007. Performance Model for Grid-
555 Connected Photovoltaic Inverters, SAND2007-5036. *Contract* 38, 655–660.

556 Lefèvre, M., Oumbe, A., Blanc, P., Espinar, B., Gschwind, B., Qu, Z., Wald, L., Schroedter-
557 Homscheidt, M., Hoyer-Klick, C., Arola, A., Benedetti, A., Kaiser, J.W., Morcrette, J.-J.,
558 2013. McClear: a new model estimating downwelling solar radiation at ground level in
559 clear-sky conditions. *Atmos. Meas. Tech* 6, 2403–2418. doi:10.5194/amt-6-2403-2013

560 Lindberg, F., Grimmond, C.S.B., 2010. Continuous sky view factor maps from high resolution
561 urban digital elevation models. *Climate Research* 42, 177–183. doi:10.3354/cr00882

562 Lindberg, F., Jonsson, P., Honjo, T., Wästberg, D., 2015. Solar energy on building envelopes –
563 3D modelling in a 2D environment. *Solar Energy* 115, 369–378.
564 doi:10.1016/j.solener.2015.03.001

565 Lou, S., Li, D.H.W., Lam, J.C., Lee, E.W.M., 2016. Estimation of obstructed vertical solar
566 irradiation under the 15 CIE Standard Skies. *Building and Environment* 103, 123–133.
567 doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.04.005

568 Marchand, M., Ghennioui, A., Wey, E., Wald, L., 2018. Comparison of several satellite-derived
569 databases of surface solar radiation against ground measurement in Morocco. *Adv. Sci.*
570 *Res* 15, 21–29. doi:10.5194/asr-15-21-2018

571 Marszal, A.J., Heiselberg, P., Bourrelle, J.S., Musall, E., Voss, K., Sartori, I., Napolitano, A., 2011.
572 Zero Energy Building - A review of definitions and calculation methodologies. *Energy and*
573 *Buildings* 43, 971–979. doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2010.12.022

574 Martín-Chivelet, N., Gutiérrez, J.C., Alonso-Abella, M., Chenlo, F., Cuenca, J., 2018. Building
575 retrofit with photovoltaics: Construction and performance of a BIPV ventilated façade.
576 *Energies* 11. doi:10.3390/en11071719

577 Martínez-Moreno, F., Muñoz, J., Lorenzo, E., 2010. Experimental model to estimate shading
578 losses on PV arrays. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 94, 2298–2303.
579 doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2010.07.029

580 Masa-Bote, D., Caamaño-Martín, E., 2014. Methodology for estimating building integrated
581 photovoltaics electricity production under shadowing conditions and case study.
582 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 31, 492–500. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2013.12.019

583 Perez, R., Ineichen, P., Seals, R., Michalsky, J., Stewart, R., 1990. Modeling daylight availability
584 and irradiance components from direct and global irradiance. *Solar Energy* 44, 271–289.
585 doi:10.1016/0038-092X(90)90055-H

586 Perez, R., Seals, R., Ineichen, P., Stewart, R., Menicucci, D., 1987. A new simplified version of

587 the perez diffuse irradiance model for tilted surfaces. *Solar Energy* 39, 221–231.
588 doi:10.1016/S0038-092X(87)80031-2

589 Polo, J., Alonso-García, M.C., Silva, J.P., Alonso-Abella, M., 2016. Modelling the performance of
590 rooftop photovoltaic systems under urban Mediterranean outdoor conditions. *Journal of*
591 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 8, 013502. doi:10.1063/1.4942856

592 Polo, J., Fernández-Peruchena, C., Salamalakis, V., Mazorra-Aguiar, L., Turpin, M., Martín-
593 Pomares, L., Kazantzidis, A., Blanc, P., Remund, J., 2020. Benchmarking on improvement
594 and site-adaptation techniques for modeled solar radiation datasets. *Solar Energy* 201,
595 469–479. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2020.03.040

596 Polo, J., Perez, R., 2019. Solar radiation modeling from satellite imagery, in: Polo, J.; Martín-
597 Pomares, L., Sanfilippo, A. (Ed.), *Solar Resource Mapping - Fundamentals and*
598 *Applications; Green Energy and Technology*. Springer, pp. 183–197. doi:10.1007/978-3-
599 319-97484-2_6

600 Psiloglou, B.E., Kambezidis, H.D., Kaskaoutis, D.G., Karagiannis, D., Polo, J.M., 2020.
601 Comparison between MRM simulations, CAMS and PVGIS databases with measured solar
602 radiation components at the Methoni station, Greece. *Renewable Energy* 146, 1372–
603 1391. doi:10.1016/J.RENENE.2019.07.064

604 PVPCM, 2021. PV LIB [WWW Document]. URL [https://pvpmc.sandia.gov/applications/pv_lib-](https://pvpmc.sandia.gov/applications/pv_lib-toolbox/)
605 [toolbox/](https://pvpmc.sandia.gov/applications/pv_lib-toolbox/) (accessed 6.8.21).

606 PVPS, I., 2021. Enabling Framework for the Development of BIPV [WWW Document]. Web
607 page. URL [https://iea-pvps.org/research-tasks/enabling-framework-for-the-](https://iea-pvps.org/research-tasks/enabling-framework-for-the-development-of-bipv/)
608 [development-of-bipv/](https://iea-pvps.org/research-tasks/enabling-framework-for-the-development-of-bipv/) (accessed 6.8.21).

609 QGIS, 2021. A Free and Open Source Geographic Information System [WWW Document]. URL
610 <https://www.qgis.org/en/site/> (accessed 6.8.21).

611 Qu, Z., Gschwind, B., Lefevre, M., Wald, L., Oumbe, A., Blanc, P., Espinar, B., Gesell, G.,
612 Gschwind, B., Klüser, L., Lefèvre, M., Saboret, L., Schroedter-Homscheidt, M., Wald, L.,
613 2017. Fast radiative transfer parameterisation for assessing the surface solar irradiance:
614 The Heliosat-4 method. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift* 26, 33–57.
615 doi:10.1127/metz/2016/0781

616 Ratti, C., Richens, P., 1999. Urban Texture Analysis with Image Processing Techniques, in: CAAD
617 Futures99. Atlanta.

618 Redweik, P., Catita, C., Brito, M., 2013. Solar energy potential on roofs and facades in an urban
619 landscape. *Solar Energy* 97, 332–341. doi:10.1016/J.SOLENER.2013.08.036

620 Riihelä, A., Carlund, T., Trentmann, J., Müller, R., Lindfors, A., 2015. Validation of CM SAF
621 Surface Solar Radiation Datasets over Finland and Sweden. *Remote Sensing* 7, 6663–
622 6682. doi:10.3390/rs70606663

623 Schroedter-Homscheidt, M., Hoyer-Klick, C., Killius, N., Betcke, J., Lefèvre, M., Wald, L., Wey,
624 E., Saboret, L., 2019. User ' s Guide to the CAMS Radiation Service (CRS) Status
625 December 2019. ECMWF Copernicus Report.

626 Sengupta, M., Habte, A., Gueymard, C., Wilbert, S., Renné, D., 2017. Best Practices Handbook
627 for the Collection and Use of Solar Resource Data for Solar Energy Applications: Second
628 Edition. doi:10.18777/ieashc-task46-2015-0001

629 Seyedmahmoudian, M., Mekhilef, S., Rahmani, R., Yusof, R., Renani, E., 2013. Analytical
630 Modeling of Partially Shaded Photovoltaic Systems. *Energies* 6, 128–144.
631 doi:10.3390/en6010128

632 Singh, R., Banerjee, R., 2015. Estimation of rooftop solar photovoltaic potential of a city. *Solar*
633 *Energy* 115, 589–602. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2015.03.016

634 Stein, J.S., Farnung, B., 2017. PV Performance Modeling Methods and Practices Results from
635 the 4th PV Performance Modeling Collaborative Workshop. IEA PVPS Task 13, Subtask 2
636 Report IEA-PVPS T13-06:2017.

637 Urraca, R., Martinez-De-Pison, E., Sanz-Garcia, A., Antonanzas, J., Antonanzas-Torres, F., 2017.
638 Estimation methods for global solar radiation: Case study evaluation of five different

639 approaches in central Spain. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.222
640 Verso, A., Martin, A., Amador, J., Dominguez, J., 2015. GIS-based method to evaluate the
641 photovoltaic potential in the urban environments: The particular case of Miraflores de la
642 Sierra. Solar Energy 117, 236–245. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2015.04.018
643 Walch, A., Castello, R., Mohajeri, N., Scartezzini, J.L., 2020. Big data mining for the estimation
644 of hourly rooftop photovoltaic potential and its uncertainty. Applied Energy 262, 114404.
645 doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114404
646 Yang, D., 2016. Solar radiation on inclined surfaces: Corrections and benchmarks. Solar Energy.
647 doi:10.1016/j.solener.2016.06.062
648 Yang, D., 2018. A correct validation of the National Solar Radiation Data Base (NSRDB).
649 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 97, 152–155.
650 doi:10.1016/J.RSER.2018.08.023
651 Yang, D., Bright, J.M., 2020. Worldwide validation of 8 satellite-derived and reanalysis solar
652 radiation products: A preliminary evaluation and overall metrics for hourly data over 27
653 years. Solar Energy. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2020.04.016
654